

Storage at the Edge^{*}

Investigating distributed storage solutions for the edge computing paradigm

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Abstract. The proliferation of Internet of Things and the success of rich cloud services have pushed the horizon of a new computing paradigm, Edge computing, which calls for processing the data at the edge of the network. Similar to Cloud, Edge computing provides data, computing, storage, and application services to end-users. Edge computing has the potential to address the concerns of response time requirement, battery life constraint, bandwidth cost saving, as well as data safety and privacy. Such paradigm requires shifting the storage facilities to the edge of the backbone in order to bring Cloud computing resources closer to the end-user. Although the infrastructures and technologies used in centralized Cloud storage are well studied, the design of a decentralized storage at the Edge has not yet been discussed. The recent evolution of the storage hierarchy has seen the emergence of new technologies such as Open-channel SSDs, which allow the separation of host, storage and controller. In this paper we argue that this storage architecture is well fitted for the Edge computing paradigm. We also explore how existing approaches can be used to design the infrastructure needed for Edge storage.

Keywords: Cloud computing; Edge computing; Decentralized storage system; Open-channel SSD

1 Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) typically involves numerous smart sensors sensing information from the environment and sharing it to a cloud service for processing.

This leads to two major issues for computing IoT-generated data: the processing time of time-critical IoT applications can be limited by the network delay for offloading data to cloud, and uploading data from many IoT generators may induce network congestion thus incurring further network delay.

Cloud computing has evolved as the key computing infrastructure for Internet to become the overarching Internet approach for information storage, retrieval and management. This however faces several fundamental challenges: agility of services, real-time response, or long-thin connection.

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To overcome above issues between Cloud and mobile applications, Edge computing has recently emerged as a more practical solution to enable the smooth convergence between cloud and mobile for content delivery and real-time data processing.

The idea of fog computing (see Figure 1) is to place light-weight cloud-like facility at the proximity of mobile users, therefore allowing the edge to serve mobile users with a direct short-fat connection as compared to the long-thin mobile cloud connection. More importantly, as deployed at localized sites, edge computing can provide customized and engaged location-aware services which are more desirable to mobile users.

Fig. 1: Edge computing paradigm

This paradigm shift introduces new challenges with data storage. The current approach for data storage and processing is that one unit—possibly geographically distributed among multiple datacenters or racks—manages the whole chain. Bringing the computing power to the edge, in a decentralized and distributed environment is challenging and asks for a new design in the way data is accessed, stored and processed.

The introduction of blockchains as a way to provide consensus for a decentralized cryptocurrency has allowed numerous experiments in blockchain-based decentralized cloud-like services, such as computing platform [9], database [18], or object storage [33].

Contributions Section 2 describes the recent evolution of the storage hierarchy and the new storage device considered in this paper. Section 3 presents a general view of the current approach for storage in the Cloud, and some technologies used in this centralized environment. We present our view of a storage system at the Edge in Section 4, along with a background on related software. Section 5 discusses the challenges related to decentralized storage. We conclude in Section 6.

2 Architecture

In this section give an overview the new architecture considered in this paper. We present recent storage technologies, Open-channel SSDs and DragonFire Card, in the context of Edge computing.

Solid State Drives Solid State Drives (SSDs) are composed of tens of non-volatile memory chips wired in parallel to a controller via multiple channels. Each chip is organized in planes, blocks and pages. Most commercial SSDs expose an interface similar to hard-disk drives. A component residing in the SSD controller (see Figure 2a), called Flash Translation Layer (FTL), hides the inner characteristics of flash memory and expose only an array of logical block addresses to the host.

Open-channel Open-channel SSDs do not have a FTL, and expose their internals, sharing the management of the physical storage with the host operating system (see Figure 2b), whereas a traditional SSDs keep its functionalities strictly in firmware.

Fig. 2: Evolution of SSD controllers

DragonFire Card In this work we consider a programmable SSD device, the DragonFire Card (DFC). The DFC is composed of two boards connected by PCI Express: a system on chip (SoC) (e.g. LS2088A from NXP) and a storage board consisting of a field-programmable gate array (FPGA) and dual in-line memory modules (DIMMs), or M.2 connectors with a commercial SSD. The SoC board can be connected to a host computer to serve as an interface between the storage board and the host (see Figure 2c), and typically provides a Linux operating system and manages the network.

3 Centralized Storage

In this section we review the general architecture used in centralized cloud and some technologies that can be deployed in this context.

Fig. 3: Cloud

3.1 Architectural design of data centers

The current Cloud is built top of geographically distributed data centers.

A data center, which is home to the computation power and storage, is central to cloud computing and contains thousands of devices like servers, switches and routers.

The conventional topology used in data centers follows a hierarchical approach, as do the global architecture of the Internet. It can typically be decomposed into three layers, depicted on Figure 4. The basic layers of a data center consist of the core, aggregation, and access layers.

The access layer is where the servers in racks physically connect to the network.

The aggregation layer usually provides functions such as domain service, location service, server load balancing, and more.

The core layer provides secure connectivity between aggregation switches and core routers connected to the Internet. The core routers manage traffic into and out of the data center

Although one service can be distributed across multiple racks and data centers, the whole infrastructure is often considered as one unit of management, thanks to the aggregations layer. Every device inside one unit fully trusts every other device of the unit. This abstraction is possible because all devices lives inside the same trusted infrastructure.

3.2 Remote Direct Memory Access

Remote direct memory access (RDMA) is a mechanism that enable out of user space operations to a remote memory buffer without operating system involvement. This permits high-throughput, low-latency networking. RDMA is widely deployed in high-performance computing.

RDMA allows zero-copy networking—i.e. applications can perform data transfer without the network software stack involvement (see Figure 5), therefore allowing data to be sent and received directly to the buffers without being copied between the network layers, and can bypass the kernel, transferring directly from

Fig. 4: Conventional data center network topology

userspace without the need to perform context switches. The remote CPU is not involved during the data transfer.

Several network protocols support RDMA, such as InfiniBand (IB), RDMA Over Converged Ethernet (RoCE), and Internet Wide Area RDMA Protocol (iWARP).

Fig. 5: RDMA Stack

3.3 InfiniBand

The InfiniBand Architecture [11] (IBA) defines a switched network fabric for interconnecting processing nodes and I/O nodes. It provides a communication and management infrastructure for interprocessor communication and I/O. In an

InfiniBand network, processing nodes and I/O nodes are connected to the fabric by channel adapters (CAs). Channel adapters usually have programmable direct memory access (DMA) engines with protection features. There are two kinds of channel adapters: host channel adapter (HCA) and target channel adapter (TCA). HCAs sit on processing nodes.

The InfiniBand communication stack consists of different layers. The interface presented by channel adapters to consumers belongs to the transport layer. A queue-based model is used in this interface. A queue pair in InfiniBand Architecture consists of two queues: a send queue and a receive queue. The send queue holds instructions to transmit data, and the receive queue holds instructions that describe where received data is to be placed. Communication operations are described in work queue requests (WQRs), or descriptors, and are submitted to the work queue. The completion of WQRs is reported through completion queues (CQs). Once a work queue element is finished, a completion queue entry is placed in the associated completion queue. Applications can check the completion queue to see whether any work queue request has been finished. InfiniBand also supports different classes of transport service.

The interested reader is referred to [24] for an in-depth review of InfiniBand Architecture.

3.4 NVMe over Fabrics

Non-Volatile Memory Express (NVMe) is a logical device interface specification for accessing SSDs.

Fig. 6: NVM Express over Fabrics

NVMe over Fabrics (see Figure 6) is a specification designed to enable NVMe message-based commands to transfer data between a host computer and a target SSD or system over a network such as Ethernet, Fibre Channel, and InfiniBand.

4 Decentralized Storage

In this section we first describe the basis of a decentralized storage infrastructure and underline the key differences with its centralized counterpart. We then review recent software that propose such a system.

We consider a city-wide decentralized network of heterogeneous nodes—similar to the DFC described in Section 2—at the edge of the network. Contrary to the centralized model, the network is composed of multiple units grouping hosts, controllers and disks, as depicted on Figure 7. While devices inside a same unit trust each other, two different units do not.

The base requirements of a storage service is that any node of the system must be able to add and get data from the store. Other common properties include replication of data, access management [20], etc.

Fig. 7: Example of network topology considered in this paper

4.1 Discovering and Exchanging

Multiple software provide the building block for a decentralized storage system, that is a way to discover and exchange files between peers.

InterPlanetary File System InterPlanetary File System [13] (IPFS) is a protocol designed to create a permanent and decentralized method of storing and sharing files. It is inspired by the technologies of BitTorrent and Git.

IPFS is transport agnostic, so it can run over any transport protocol (eg. TCP, UDP), and on any Internet architecture (eg. NDN [22], XIA [6]). It defines a content-addressable (ie. a resource is retrieved based on its content, not its location) network overlay.

Files in IPFS are immutable. Similar to the Git version manager, instead of “replacing” a file, the new version is added to the network, with a pointer to the original version.

IPFS uses a block storage logic—it emulates the behavior of a traditional block device, such as a physical hard drive, and storage is organized as sequence of bytes having a maximum length—and provides a file system abstraction.

Tahoe Least-Authority File Store Tahoe Least-Authority File Store [29] (Tahoe-LAFS) is a decentralized data store and file system designed around the “principle of least privilege”. It uses cryptographic capabilities to handle read, write and verify access on mutable and immutable files and directories. A capability is a communicable, unforgeable token of authority. It refers to a value that references an object along with an associated set of access rights. The capabilities provide a content-addressable network.

Tahoe-LAFS makes use of with Reed-Solomon [26] erasure coding to provide RAID-like replication. Tahoe-LAFS assumes that two users willing to share data are able to discover themselves and securely exchange capabilities.

GlusterFS GlusterFS [8] is a scale-out network-attached storage POSIX file system. Functionalities include file-based mirroring and replication, file-based striping, file-based load balancing, volume failover, scheduling and disk caching, storage quotas, and volume snapshots with user serviceability. GlusterFS follows a client-server architecture, where servers are viewed as pool by a client. Network discovery is unspecified. It is assumed the servers inside a pool are trusted.

Infini Infini [12] is a distributed key-value store built on top of an overlay network and a distributed hash table by aggregating storage capacity from a collection of servers. It provides resilience through redundancy and fault tolerance.

4.2 Blockchain

For a storage platform to provide replication, access control, or other form of constrained storage, there must be a way for a node to ask for other nodes to store its data.

The absence of trust between participants introduce the need for a consensus algorithm. Using a consensus protocol, such as Paxos [16], to achieve agreement among the peers can incur substantial overhead when coordination is required in a Byzantine setting.

Blockchain [34,30,10] has been introduced in 2008 by Nakamoto as a way to obtain a relaxed consensus in an untrusted asynchronous decentralized environment. The blockchain algorithm in itself is outside the scope of this work, we only give a brief overview of the protocol.

A blockchain is a protocol in which each user possesses a variable state containing blocks. Blocks themselves contains a set of messages and a header pointing at the most recently created block before them. The blocks thus form a chronologically ordered chain. There are three types of nodes in the network: players, who create messages and broadcasts them to the network; miners who build blocks by collecting the messages they receive (once a block is mined, this

block is broadcast within the network); users who add the blocks they receive into the blockchain if and only if all the messages they contain are valid.

In order to preserve the unicity of the chain shared by all users, a blockchain protocol provides a deterministic algorithm to select a particular branch—thus transforming a tree back into a chain—, along with an algorithm, such as proof-of-work [5] or proof-of-stake [2], which allows blocks to be added to the chain in a desynchronised fashion, while protecting from denial of service attacks and abuses.

4.3 Constrained Storage

Multiple blockchain have been proposed as way to incentive nodes to host each other's data. In these systems, a client need to spend tokens (i.e. some form of currency) to host its data, whereas a host receive tokens for offering its disk space.

Storj [33], *Sia* [31], and *Filecoin* [7] are the most known decentralized marketplace for Cloud storage using a blockchain. The three protocols use a blockchain as an open ledger of contracts between users. A contract is established each time a user need to send data into the system.

Storj uses a trusted platform as a gateway into the system. The platform receives hosting requirements from a client and forward them to available peers.

The need for a centralized platform is mainly due to the way Storj ensures a client that its data is safely stored and on some peer's disk and available. To verify the availability and integrity, the platform asks the host to compute a checksum on a subset of the data, which is compared to a pre-computed checksum. This follows a heartbeat protocol.

Sia and Filecoin makes uses of smart contracts to enforce redundancy and availability. Smart contracts are small programs executed by every participant of a blockchain. A smart contract need to respect the properties of a blockchain: every peer, at any time, must obtain the same output and be able to verify the output. In Sia or Filecoin, a smart contract is associated to a transaction between a client and some hosts. For example, the smart contract can state that payment will be made (automatically) to the hosts if a given file is hosted for a given period of time.

MaidSAFE is another storage marketplace. In MaidSAFE, tokens a paid on data retrieval. The amount of tokens someone can earn is directly linked to the resources they provide and how often their computer is turned on.

Permacoin [19] and KopperCoin [14] are two blockchains designed for storage, which do not make use of a proof-of-work during the block creating. This makes the schemes energy efficient.

Ethereum's Swarm was conceived of as a storage protocol tailored for inter-operation with the Ethereum smart contract ecosystem. It makes uses of the Ethereum's consensus proces. Swarm takes the approach of rewarding nodes for serving content. Because more often requested content is more profitable to store

than rarely requested content, rewarding nodes only for recall would incentivise the trashing of rarely accessed data.

5 Discussion

In this section we discuss some challenges and underline solutions proposed by the tools reviewed in Section 4.

5.1 Content-addressable

Most storage systems deployed today (e.g. the Internet, or file systems used in computers) use paths to access its resources. To access a given file, an application must know its location (or address). For conventional file systems, the location is a name and a path in a hierarchy of directories.

This approach, referred as location-addressed, suffers from several drawbacks in a distributed environment. The main problem is that given only a file location on a distant server, it is impossible for a client to know if the file has changed or has been removed. Using a checksum with the location, a client is able to verify the data integrity, but has no way to find the requested file in case the checksum test fails.

Content-addressable systems have been proposed to cope with this issue. In a content-addressable system, the identifier of a file is derived from the content of the file.

Content-addressable systems also provide deduplication by design if the identifier of a file is deterministic.

Content-addressable memory has been proposed [23], which could be used on SSD to implement a content-addressable system on both SSD's blocks and network levels.

To use a blockchain in the context of file sharing, there must be an immutable way to reference a file. The reference must be the same at all time for the chain to be verifiable by the peers. A content-addressable storage provides such a property.

However, locating the last version of a file in a content-addressable system can be challenging. IPFS proposes to use Domain Name Servers (DNS) to cope with this problem. A DNS server associates an unchanging link (e.g. a domain name) to some changing content (e.g. an IP address) for a determined period of time. This proposition could use a system such as Namecoin [21] which provides a decentralized censorship resistant DNS registrar based on blockchain.

5.2 Scalability and Efficiency

Although DFCs are power efficient embedded devices, obtaining consensus is costly, both in term of network overhead and power consumption.

Proof-of-work mechanisms used in blockchain-based systems are often criticized for their energy cost [36]. On the other hand, proof-of-stake mechanisms are

often a treat to the fairness of blockchain networks [3]. Fairness in bitcoin-based cryptocurrencies has been surveyed in [35].

Using a “useful” computation for the proof-of-work, instead of the classic hash inversion, would mitigate the energy efficiency problem. Primecoin [25] is an example, which is proof-of-work based on searching for prime numbers. [36] proposes to use multiple consensus algorithms, on different levels.

A framework for blockchains benchmarking [4] has been proposed. It allows the comparison of different blockchains on overall and component-wise performance in terms of throughput, latency, scalability and fault-tolerance.

5.3 Security and Privacy

Security and privacy protection in Cloud are being explored by many researchers [32]. Storage security can be provided using erasure-correcting codes [37]. Authentication of users using public key cryptographic techniques has been studied in [17]. Many homomorphic encryption techniques have been suggested [28] to ensure that the Cloud is not able to read the data while performing computations on them.

A decentralized data storage platform can use similar solutions to cope with issues related to security and privacy. Dynamic access control in a decentralized environment is however challenging. [27] proposes a decentralized access control technique with anonymous authentication.

The use of a blockchain as the central ledger of the platform introduce privacy issues, as its main role is to be traceable. Privacy-preserving smart contracts [15] have been proposed but require multi-party computation (MPC) techniques which introduce an important overhead to the system.

Today, most embedded devices, such as DFCs, are equipped with trusted hardware and cryptographic hardware accelerators which can be used to accelerate MPC and would allow the heavy schemes required for a secure and privacy-preserving system. [1] is an example of database making use of this hardware.

6 Conclusion

We have discussed the key differences that opposes centralized storage in the Cloud and decentralized storage for the Edge paradigm. Recent advances in storage technology is the key to such a paradigm shift. We reviewed multiple “off-the-shelf” tools that try to propose a decentralized storage system, and discusses the challenges they face.

Storing data often implies the need for data processing. Decentralized processing at the Edge has been proposed by tools such as Golem [9] but not intensively studied. This is obviously the next step for this work.

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References

1. Bajaj, S., Sion, R.: Trusteddb: A trusted hardware-based database with privacy and data confidentiality. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 26(3), 752–765 (2014)
2. Bentov, I., Gabizon, A., Mizrahi, A.: Cryptocurrencies without proof of work. In: *International Conference on Financial Cryptography and Data Security*. pp. 142–157. Springer (2016)
3. Bentov, I., Pass, R., Shi, E.: Snow white: Provably secure proofs of stake. *IACR Cryptology ePrint Archive* 2016, 919 (2016)
4. Dinh, T.T.A., Wang, J., Chen, G., Liu, R., Ooi, B.C., Tan, K.L.: Blockbench: A framework for analyzing private blockchains. In: *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM International Conference on Management of Data*. pp. 1085–1100. ACM (2017)
5. Dwork, C., Naor, M.: Pricing via processing or combatting junk mail. In: *Annual International Cryptology Conference*. pp. 139–147. Springer (1992)
6. expressive internet architecture project, <https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~xia/>
7. Filecoin: A decentralized storage network (2017), <https://filecoin.io>
8. Glusterfs network filesystem, <https://www.gluster.org>
9. Golem worldwide supercomputer, <https://golem.network>
10. Hari, A., Lakshman, T.: The internet blockchain: A distributed, tamper-resistant transaction framework for the internet. In: *Proceedings of the 15th ACM Workshop on Hot Topics in Networks*. pp. 204–210. ACM (2016)
11. InfiniBandSM Trade Association: InfiniBandTM Architecture Specification <http://infinibandta.org>
12. Infinit storage platform, <http://infinit.sh>
13. Interplanetary file system: hypermedia distribution protocol (2014), <https://ipfs.io>
14. Kopp, H., Bösch, C., Kargl, F.: Koppercoin—a distributed file storage with financial incentives. In: *International Conference on Information Security Practice and Experience*. pp. 79–93. Springer (2016)
15. Kosba, A., Miller, A., Shi, E., Wen, Z., Papamanthou, C.: Hawk: The blockchain model of cryptography and privacy-preserving smart contracts. In: *Security and Privacy (SP), 2016 IEEE Symposium on*. pp. 839–858. IEEE (2016)
16. Lamport, L.: Time, clocks, and the ordering of events in a distributed system. *Communications of the ACM* 21(7), 558–565 (1978)
17. Li, H., Dai, Y., Tian, L., Yang, H.: Identity-based authentication for cloud computing. *Cloud computing* pp. 157–166 (2009)
18. McConaghy, T., Marques, R., Müller, A., De Jonghe, D., McConaghy, T., McMullen, G., Henderson, R., Bellemare, S., Granzotto, A.: Bigchaindb: a scalable blockchain database (2016), <http://bigchaindb.com>
19. Miller, A., Juels, A., Shi, E., Parno, B., Katz, J.: Permacoin: Repurposing bitcoin work for data preservation. In: *Security and Privacy (SP), 2014 IEEE Symposium on*. pp. 475–490. IEEE (2014)

20. Müller, A., Ludwig, A., Franczyk, B.: Data security in decentralized cloud systems—system comparison, requirements analysis and organizational levels. *Journal of Cloud Computing* 6(1), 15 (2017)
21. Namecoin, <https://namecoin.org>
22. Named data networking project, <https://named-data.net>
23. Pagiantzis, K., Sheikholeslami, A.: Content-addressable memory (cam) circuits and architectures: a tutorial and survey. *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits* 41(3), 712–727 (March 2006)
24. Panda, D.K., Sur, S.: Infiniband. In: *Encyclopedia of Parallel Computing*, pp. 927–935. Springer US, Boston, MA (2011)
25. Primecoin cryptocurrency, <http://primecoin.io>
26. Reed, I.S., Solomon, G.: Polynomial codes over certain finite fields. *Journal of the society for industrial and applied mathematics* 8(2), 300–304 (1960)
27. Ruj, S., Stojmenovic, M., Nayak, A.: Decentralized access control with anonymous authentication of data stored in clouds. *IEEE transactions on parallel and distributed systems* 25(2), 384–394 (2014)
28. Sadeghi, A.R., Schneider, T., Winandy, M.: Token-based cloud computing. In: *International Conference on Trust and Trustworthy Computing*. pp. 417–429. Springer (2010)
29. Selimi, M., Freitag, F.: Tahoe-lafs distributed storage service in community network clouds. In: *Big Data and Cloud Computing (BdCloud), 2014 IEEE Fourth International Conference on*. pp. 17–24. IEEE (2014)
30. Shafagh, H., Hithnawi, A., Duquennoy, S.: Towards blockchain-based auditable storage and sharing of iot data (2017)
31. Sia: Simple decentralized storage (2014), <http://sia.tech>
32. Slamanig, D., Hanser, C.: On cloud storage and the cloud of clouds approach. In: *Internet Technology And Secured Transactions, 2012 International Conference for*. pp. 649–655. IEEE (2012)
33. Storj: peer-to-peer cloud storage network (2014), <http://storj.io>
34. Sun, J., Yan, J., Zhang, K.Z.: Blockchain-based sharing services: What blockchain technology can contribute to smart cities. *Financial Innovation* 2(1), 26 (2016)
35. Tschorsch, F., Scheuermann, B.: Bitcoin and beyond: A technical survey on decentralized digital currencies. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 18(3), 2084–2123 (2016)
36. Vukolić, M.: The quest for scalable blockchain fabric: Proof-of-work vs. bft replication. In: *International Workshop on Open Problems in Network Security*. pp. 112–125. Springer (2015)
37. Wang, C., Wang, Q., Ren, K., Cao, N., Lou, W.: Toward secure and dependable storage services in cloud computing. *IEEE transactions on Services Computing* 5(2), 220–232 (2012)